

ORGANISATION SCHEMES OF HISTORY WEBSITES: A QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT

Final Report

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this report is to provide a review on the types of organisation schemes employed within history websites across a number of subject areas.

Emergent digital communication technologies has seen the digital historian focus on the tools available to them when presenting a narrative, neglecting how information may best be organised within a website. Information Architects meanwhile have focused their organisation skills and energies upon projects that have overlooked the role of organisation schemes within history websites. The current research project aims to fill this gap.

A quantitative research approach was conducted employing purposive nonprobability sampling for website selection through a website portal, *besthistorysites.net*, a closed-ended questionnaire for data collection and bivariate descriptive analysis for data analysis to answer the question: Do organisational scheme(s) employed within history websites change dependent upon the subject matter involved?

Findings show that while different types of organisation schemes are employed within history websites, their use is not related to either the subject matter, the creator of the website or when the website was built as to the use of any particular organisation scheme. Instead, a consistent pattern emerges across all fields of history subjects that were reviewed. Additionally, the research determined that a high level use of hybrid schemes were employed within all subject matters reviewed in a consistent pattern.

The report finds that while different types of organisation are employed within history websites, their use is not related to the subject matter. Instead, factors associated with the type of content, audience needs and the overall goal of the project are likely to influence which organisation scheme is employed.

Recommendations for future research includes examining the potential for primary sources to act as a standalone organisation scheme for history websites; a review of audience-specific schemes within history websites to determine how this scheme may impact upon historical understand; and conducting the same questionnaire on contemporary history websites that are purposively built by digital historians.

Research was limited due to the categorisation of history websites within *besthistorysites.net*, the age of the websites that were selected for assessment and a lack of access to statistical software required for data analysis.

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1.0 Introduction

Digital history is a board and emergent field, 'directly engaged with the role new digital technologies can play in presenting and representing the past' (Weller, 2013). Where history has traditionally being communicated through books and journal articles, websites have added another dimension to how history may be conveyed (Cohen & Rosenweig, 2006). The linear narrative of a book is now countered by the flexible digital environment, a space where information needs to be organised in a way that makes sense to its reader (Covert, 2014). There are many organisation schemes through which information may be organised within a website. This research project will examine the types of organisation schemes found within history websites, determining the frequency of the schemes across a wide range of historical subject matters.

This report provides the rationale of the project, identifying the scope, objectives, outcomes and significance along with the research question posed. A literature review is presented, signifying the gap within organisation schemes and history website literature. The research approach is detailed, covering website selection, questionnaire development, piloting along with the data collection and data analysis phase. Findings are then presented, summarising the use of organisational schemes. A discussion on these findings then takes place before limitations of the project are provided and recommendations for future research stated. A conclusion summarises the report while the appendices includes details of the questionnaire and findings too detailed to include within the report.

2.0 Purpose

The purpose of this research project is to determine the types of organisation schemes employed within history websites across a variety of subject matters. A rationale for the research project is provided, followed by the scope, objectives, outcomes and finally the significance.

2.1 Rationale

Historical research and scholarship have been impacted by the development of emergent technologies and it is now commonly accepted within the historical profession that new communication technologies are playing a critical role in how history is presented (Cohen et al., 2008; Marwick, 2001; Weller, 2013). While some historians have been hesitant to change, continuing to apply their tradecraft via traditional methods, others have jumped at the opportunity to explore the possibilities of how digital tools may impact both the historical research process and the narratives derived from them when developing history websites. Often forgotten, however, has been any discussion relating to how information is to be organised, a concern when it is considered that different historical subject matters may have different information organisation needs when presenting narratives on the web.

Through a 'thoughtful contriving of ontology, taxonomy, and choreography' (Klyn, 2016), information architecture (IA) is the 'practice of deciding how to arrange the parts of something to be understandable' (IA Institute, n.d.). A practice that makes complex information environments clear. Nestled under the umbrella of IA are organisation schemes, a practice that 'defines the shared characteristics of content items and influences the logical grouping of those items' (Morville, Rosenfeld, & Arango, 2015). Through organising information, capabilities are created, thereby increasing value (Glushko, 2013) and creating understanding. There are many schemes which may be employed within a history website and each scheme has the ability to influence understanding (Wurman, Leifer, Sume, & Whitehouse, 2001). While considerable literature exists on the types of

organisation schemes available in addition to studies relating to commercial and non-commercial projects, currently no research on the organisational schemes of history websites has been conducted.

This research project aims to address the gap in the literature on organisation schemes as they relate to history websites, determining the types of schemes that are employed, their frequency of occurrence and the use of multiple schemes across various subject matters.

2.2 Research Question

Do organisational scheme(s) employed within history websites change dependent upon the subject matter involved?

2.3 Objectives

The objectives of this project are:

1. Determine the types of organisational scheme(s) that are employed within existing history websites by subject matter.
2. Determine if particular subject matters have a frequency of employing one type of organisational scheme over another.
3. Determine the prevalence of history websites that employ more than one organisational scheme to present content.

2.4 Scope

This research project assesses the organisation schemes of history websites across a wide range of subject matters. Historical enquiry is broad in scope, covering everything to do with the past. Within the discipline are a number of categories which may include social, political, gender, economic, ethnicity and race history (Munslow, 2012). Each category of history features many sub-categories that may be based on a specific time period, or are religious, thematic or are nationalist in focus. This research project aims to explore a diverse cross-section of history websites to best answer the research question and meet the objectives of the project.

2.5 Outcomes

The outcomes of this research project are directly aligned with the objectives:

1. An understanding of the types of organisation schemes that are employed across various historical subject matters, including the frequency of hybrid scheme employment.
2. Recommendations for further research towards the types of organisation schemes employed within history websites across various subject matter.

2.6 Significance

The significance of this research project are:

1. It will add to the existing information architecture literature with respect to organisation schemes. The existing information architecture literature has yet to look at history websites and how information is organised.
2. The research will provide focus for the historian when developing websites on the types of organisation schemes available to them. Currently digital historians focus upon the tools and techniques available to them and little emphasis has been given to the importance of organising information.

3. Determining which subject matters commonly employ which organisation schemes. This will provide a basis for the historian when developing new websites.

3.0 Literature Review

A literature review was conducted focusing upon two distinct fields of enquiry. The first relates to the discipline of digital history while the second concerned the use of organisation scheme that are commonly practiced within the field of IA. From these readings, a gap in the literature was determined.

3.1 Historical Research in the Digital Age

With the emergence of digital tools, historians have begun to ask 'what do they do to our sense of history as a mode of interrogation/knowledge-creation/understanding' (Frisch as cited in Cohen et al., 2008). For the reader, it is argued that there must be an impact upon historical knowledge as users begin to access content within a digital environment where they dictate the narrative (Cohen et al., 2008). For the historian, tools enable 'historical research to become more data-driven and bottom-up' (ter Braake, 2016).

Historical research and narrative approaches have been impacted through the development, growth and accessibility of a wide variety of tools. Seefeldt and Thomas (2009) see the use of reference managers, Google Earth, Wikipedia, flash animation, XML coding, digital video and blogs as influencing research practices. The development of Web 2.0 technologies has seen an increase in collaboration between historians within their respective fields (Finn, 2016; Middleton & York, 2014). Historical interpretations may also be reshaped through spatial analysis, visual media and database development (Dougherty & Nawrotzki, 2013), digital mapping (Robertson, 2016), 2D and 3D modelling techniques (Westbrook & van Meeuwen, 2013) and large-scale textual analysis (Ewing, 2017). Even serving the basic, primary function of research through the digitisation of sources and documents (Weller, 2013) and the 'mass digitisation of old books' (Edelstein, 2016) has led to the historians research techniques being impacted by the digital age. Cohen and Rosenzweig (2006) move away from the tools available and discuss the visual elements of designing a website, focusing upon colour contrast, the proximity of elements within a page and the alignment of those elements for aesthetic appearance. These developments are worlds apart from traditional research practices that included the recommended use of ballpoint pens, highlighters, notepads, clipboards, staplers, binders and writing papers amongst a wide assortment of physical material (McDowell, 2002). Existing literature on digital history is concerned with the tools available to develop history websites and not how those websites may be organised.

Reviewing History

Whereas historians have focused upon digital tools when researching and presenting history in a website, users have taken a similar approach. A look at a number of history website reviews establishes what it is that reviewers are looking for. Regardless of the historical subject matter, considerations towards the content of the site along with search and navigation functionality are commonly appraised (Gibson, 2013; Kousari, 2014; Millard, 2013; Mooney, 2016; Smith, 2015). How information is organised within a website is rarely discussed (Kousari, 2014).

While acknowledging that these reviews are short, there are a number of points for consideration. Firstly, websites are the end result of a research process and reviews might assume that the organisation of a history website will be professionally conducted as historians are trained to organise notes in order to create narratives. Secondly, it may be because there is no set criteria for reviewing

a history website. Finally, it may be due to information organisation simply being forgotten amongst the excitement of looking at digital maps overlaid with historical events for example. Regardless, how information is organised within a history website is overlooked by those who review them.

Historical research in the digital age has seen historians become intrigued by the use of digital tools as a method of research and presentation. Reviewers of history websites meanwhile focus their attention upon content, search and navigation methods. In both cases, how information may be organised within a history website has been forgotten. A gap in the literature exists.

3.2 Organisation Systems

Organisational systems are critical as ‘our understanding of the world is largely determined by our ability to organise information’ (Morville et al., 2015). Glushko (2013) notes that information organisation enables ‘us to relate things to each other in terms of similarity and dissimilarity and are involved whenever we perceive, communicate, analyse, predict, or classify’. Without organisation, developing an understanding of the past may become shrouded in confusion.

One component of organisational systems is that of organisation schemes, a practice that ‘defines the shared characteristics of content items and influences the logical grouping of those items’ (Morville et al., 2015). Organisation schemes are found within everyday life. Supermarkets, for example, group foods together. Fresh fruit is kept in one section of the store while milk is in another. There is no point in having fresh fruit in multiple sections. It is not logical. The digital environment functions similarly. Information found within websites have certain characteristics that are then contextualised when grouped with other bits of information of a similar nature. Glushko (2013) notes that this organisation ‘creates capabilities’, thereby increasing the value of the information.

Information may be organised into either an exact or ambiguous scheme (Covert, 2014; Kalbach, 2007; Morville et al., 2015; Spencer, 2010, 2011). An exact scheme organises information in an easy, simple, well-defined manner, ‘there’s nothing to argue about. It just is’ (Covert, 2014). They are objective, requiring ‘little intellectual work’ (Morville et al., 2015) when organising. Commonly applied schemes include alphabetical, chronological and geographical (Morville et al., 2015) while Spencer (Spencer, 2010, 2011) argues for the inclusion of format. Ambiguous schemes are subjective, requiring greater thought in where information belongs (Covert, 2014). They include topical, task-oriented, audience-specific, metaphor-driven or a combination that may be found within a hybrid scheme (Morville et al., 2015).

Logical and semantic organisation schemes are presented as another approach to grouping schemes together (Ding & Lin, 2009). Whereas logical schemes combine exact and ambiguous schemes, semantic schemes include metadata, controlled vocabularies, faceted classification and folksonomy. Wurman et al (2001) eliminate grouping schemes together, instead arguing that the ‘ways of organising information are finite’ and can only be composed through location, alphabetically, time, category or hierarchy.

As shown in Table 1, Ding & Lin (2009) detail fourteen organisation schemes that may be found within a logical/semantic approach.

Organisation Systems	
Logical Organisation	Semantic Organisation
Alphabetical	Metadata
Numerical	Controlled Vocabulary

Chronological	Faceted Classification
Geographical	Folksonomy
Task-Oriented	
Audience-Specific	
Metaphor	
Popularity	
Relevance	
Personalisation & Customisation	

Table 1: Logical/Semantic Organisation Schemes

Considerable overlap exists within a number of logical/semantic schemes, possibly creating an issue as to which scheme is best suited for specific information. As Davis (2013) argues, people organising information may not be trained information architects. Fourteen schemes could be overwhelming when undertaking information organisation. At the other end of the spectrum, Wurman et al (2001) limits the number of schemes to five. As the authors argue, these five schemes are found from personal organisation through to multi-national corporations, from the physical to the digital world. When organising a historical website, a choice between five schemes may be too few, especially considering the development of the internet in the 16 years since initial publication of the text. The exact/ambiguous approach sits in the middle, allowing great flexibility while promoting clarity and are commonly applied within the field of information architecture.

Types of Organisation Schemes

The following schemes are commonly practiced within the field of information architecture and have strong supporting evidence of their both their value and commonality in practice.

Alphabetical Schemes

Dictionaries, glossaries, encyclopaedias and indexes are types of alphabetical schemes. Essentially any type of information that has a name associated with it can feature within an alphabetical scheme (Spencer, 2010) and it is considered as an excellent secondary scheme within a website (Morville et al., 2015; Spencer, 2010). They work best when people know what they are looking for, however the limited contextual nature of the scheme does not 'communicate anything about the relationship of the objects to one another in a meaningful way' (Kalbach, 2007).

Chronological Schemes

Chronological schemes are an excellent means to display information of a time sensitive nature with news websites one of the most noticeable (Ding & Lin, 2009; Kalbach, 2007). As with alphabetical schemes, chronological schemes will almost certainly want to be used with another scheme as long as there is agreement as to when an event took place (Morville et al., 2015). Chronological schemes are ideal for history, contextualising the narrative and aiding understanding.

Geographical Schemes

Geographical schemes are ideal 'when you are trying to examine and compare information that comes from diverse sources or locales' (Wurman et al., 2001). They work best when employed supporting another scheme and to be successful, require that the user must want information presented within a geographical scheme and users' must be able to understand how to use the scheme (Spencer, 2010, 2011). Particular historical subjects are ideal for presenting information geographically. A website

detailing the history of the Cold War will likely feature documents and articles specific to both the United States and the Soviet Union in addition to parts of Europe, Asia, Africa and South America.

Format Schemes

Employing a format scheme within history websites is beneficial if the site features an array of formats – video, audio, maps and articles for example. While Spencer (2010, 2011) advocates for the use of a format scheme, other leading information architects do not include it (Kalbach, 2007; Morville et al., 2015; Wurman et al., 2001). However, as Spencer (2010) argues, if the user expects to find information within a format scheme then it is an excellent way to organise information. As multiple formats are available when developing a Second World War website, a format scheme may be an appropriate scheme to use in conjunction with another scheme.

Topical Schemes

Topical schemes organise information of a similar nature, thereby creating ‘inherent value’ (Wurman et al., 2001) for the information and are one of the common schemes to be utilised (Morville et al., 2015; Spencer, 2010, 2011). One major issue exists when organising topically – a subjective approach is required as to where information exists within the environment, a decision that may cost clarity for the user who views information differently (Covert, 2014). Negating subjective concerns however is that a topical scheme is one of the most useful ways to organise information (Morville et al., 2015) and are able to be used with any other scheme.

Task-Oriented Schemes

Interactive sites that require user input may benefit through organising information within a task-oriented scheme (Kalbach, 2007), an approach that is best suited to small, specific tasks and sections of an information environment and not the entirety of the website (Morville et al., 2015; Spencer, 2010, 2011). While task-oriented schemes may appear easy to establish, simply drawing upon information that has been organised within a website via another scheme, they can quickly become too difficult, overly complex and ultimately redundant (Spencer, 2010).

Audience-Specific Schemes

Organising information by audience, while possible, is fraught with the perils of personalising information (Morville et al., 2015). Spencer (2010) argues that audience-specific themes will only work if there are clearly defined boundaries between audiences, if users are aware to which group they belong and the content presented does not overlap considerably between audiences. While there is value in customising content to specific user groups (Morville et al., 2015), organising information within history websites may prove problematic as it requires a value to be assigned to each piece of information. History is often understood through contextualisation and a website may become complex, confusing and a tangled mess if an audience-scheme is too heavily employed.

Choosing the Right Scheme

History websites will require different organisation schemes dependent upon both the type of content that needs to be presented, the intended audience and the overall goal of the website project (Spencer, 2010). While some websites will lean towards a certain type of scheme, others will require user testing to determine the best approach (Spencer, 2009). Morville et al (2015) state that websites

are wonderful as information can be applied across a number of organisational systems. It is important to apply the type of organisation scheme within a website that people are familiar with in the physical world (Wodtke, 2003), allowing users to more readily understand the site. This is critical as ‘each way of organising permits a different understanding’ (Wurman et al., 2001) of the information presented. Historical knowledge and understanding could conceivably change as a direct result of the organisation scheme selected.

The Issues of Hybrid Schemes

Morville et al (Morville et al., 2015) state that websites are wonderful mediums as information can be applied across a number of organisational schemes. Spencer (Spencer, 2010) argues that ‘there are no hard and fast rules’ as to which organisation scheme is utilised and a combination of them may be required. This may simply be the case of applying different schemes to different areas of the site (Garrett, 2001). Caution is given however to websites that employ deep hybrid schemes as this has the ability to break the mental model of the user as to how the site functions, thereby creating confusion (Morville et al., 2015; Wurman et al., 2001). This is evidenced through a recent analysis of Podio, a cloud-based collaboration service, that features multiple schemes, ultimately damaging the usability of the website overall (Callesen, 2014). To avoid this peril, it is recommended that the integrity of each scheme remain, allowing the users’ mental model of the site to not break (Morville et al., 2015). For history websites, this is imperative as historical understanding may be impacted through the use of a deep, hybrid scheme.

Identifying the Gap

Established authoritative works have looked at organisational schemes from a number of different perspectives. Morville et al (2015) included the schemes of news and consumer websites, university pages, museums and Facebook. Wodtke (2003) focused upon shopping websites while Spencer (2011) cited news sites, Lonely Planet, Wikipedia and Bunnings amongst many. Published journal articles have a similar broad scope of subject matter when researching organisation schemes. Recent studies have focused upon collaborative tagging schemes within digital library systems (Clements & Liew, 2016; Zaveri & Atkekar, 2014). Kim and DeCoster (2011) reviewed the organisational schemes of academic business libraries while Callesen (2014) analysed Podio, a cloud-based collaborative service. In short, reviewing, analysing and providing guidance upon organisational schemes has been conducted across a wide range of subject matter. Historical websites have thus far not been included within the literature.

Summary

Digital historians and reviewers of history websites have been excited about the tools available to them when researching and presenting history. Seemingly forgotten has been how historical information is best organised within a website to make it understandable. Similarly, while the field of IA has looked at organisation schemes from a number of perspectives, history websites have thus far not been examined. A gap in the literature of these two disciplines exists.

4.0 Research Approach

To answer the research question and meet the needs of the project, a quantitative research approach has been selected. The following details the five distinct phases of the methodology: website selection, questionnaire development, piloting, data collection and data analysis.

4.1 Website Selection

Website selection was broken down into three phases: finding a portal listing websites across a wide range of subject matter; determining which subject themes to review and lastly, determining which websites within each subject theme to review.

4.1.1 Portal Selection

To answer the research question and meet the objectives of the project, purposive nonprobability sampling has been selected as the approach to website selection, allowing for a representative selection of websites to be chosen (Battaglia, 2008). Furthermore, the researcher knowledge of historical themes allows for an intellectual say in determining which sites would best answer the research question and meet the project goals (Marshall, 1996). As the research question necessitates for organisational schemes to be reviewed across multiple historical subject matters, an existing portal was searched for via Google in the following order:

- ‘Best history websites’
- ‘Top-ranked history websites’
- ‘List of history websites’
- ‘History websites by subject matter’

From these search queries, it was determined that *besthistorysites.net* was the most appropriate portal to answer the research question and meet the objectives of the project. *Besthistorysites.net* contains links to over 1,200 hundred history websites across 8 major themes and 60 minor themes and has been recommended by many organisation including Princeton University, Teaching History Magazine, Teaching History Online and MIT Libraries amongst many others (“About Us – Best of History Web Sites,” 2014).

4.1.2 Subject Theme Selection

Due to the large number of websites and broad range of subject matters found within *besthistorysites.net*, a sample of subject matters was selected that would both answer the research question and meet the objectives of the project (refer Table 2). This selection process was based upon the researchers knowledge of history, ensuring that a diverse range of subject matters were selected that focused upon different time periods, geographic locations and likely content.

Within *besthistorysites.net*, American History is presented as one list of subject matters covering hundreds of years of history. Due to the wide array of subject matters found within, it was determined to divide this category into two based on time, Early American History and Modern American History (refer Table 2).

Additionally, Military history is featured within *besthistorysites.net* as both a major and minor subject theme.

Major Subject Theme	Minor Subject Themes
Ancient/Biblical History	Egypt Greece Rome China India Judaism
Early American History	Pre-Colonial Colonial

	Early Republic US Constitution
Modern American History	Progressive Era Roaring 20s The Great Depression Civil Rights Movement Cold War Era
European History	Medieval History Renaissance Scientific Revolution, Enlightenment & French Revolution Reformation & Discovery
Modern History	World War I World War II Hitler Stalin Middle East Conflict Cold War
Military History	Military History

Table 2: besthistorysites.net selected subject themes

4.1.3 Website Selection

Determining which websites to review within each subject matter was conducted with a number of considerations in mind. Websites were included regardless of if the content did not appear to entirely match the subject matter as assigned by ‘besthistorysites.net’, the quality of the content or the quality of the organisation schemes found within the websites themselves. Websites were excluded however, if the link was either dead, if the researcher was directed to a section of the site that was clearly not the original destination or the website acted as another portal with no narrative or contextual information given. The original goal was to examine 200-300 websites, a figure that was determined by taking into consideration the research question and objectives, the available resources for undertaking the data collection and the type of data analysis performed (Daniel, 2012). Due to the high number of dead links however, only 199 were eventually found to meet the selection criteria. For example, ‘World War I’ contained links to 14 websites, only 3 of which met selection criteria. As the research progressed, it was determined that 199 websites would be sufficient to answer the research question and meet the objectives of the project.

4.2 Questionnaire Development

Data collection was performed via a closed-ended questionnaire (refer Appendix 10.1). The advantages of this method includes practical implementation as a large amount of data can be collected within a short timeframe with results being easily coded and quantified (“The advantages and disadvantages of questionnaires,” n.d.). A closed-ended questionnaire is also considered ideal for quantitative research (“Types of Survey Questions - Closed-end or open-end?,” n.d.).

The questionnaire was divided into two sections (refer Appendix 10.1). The first section provided contextual information of the website, capturing data including when the website was created and the type of content that was featured including texts, images, videos, audio or maps.

Data relating to the types of organisation schemes that may be employed within a history website was determined from the literature review (refer Appendix 10.1). A total of eight schemes were included within the questionnaire including alphabetical, chronological, geographical, topical, task-oriented, audience-specific, metaphor-driven and format schemes. These schemes were then broken down into

further insight. For example, alphabetical schemes were segmented for data capture into the use of encyclopaedia, dictionary, glossary or index. For each scheme, an option of 'other' was given in the case that information was organised differently to what the literature said.

4.3 Piloting

Piloting was conducted upon the first two websites from each subject matter identified (refer Table 2). The purpose of this step was to check and confirm the accuracy and relevancy of the questions posed within the questionnaire. From this, a number of direct changes were made to the questionnaire:

- 'Creator' was included to determine who developed the website
- 'Audio' was included as it was determined that history websites featuring content from the 20th Century may possibly include this format.

Additionally, it was originally intended that only the homepage and primary child of the website was to be included for review. However, it was determined that this was not realistic due to the poor organisational structures of some websites. Instead, the entire website that contained relevant material, regardless of hierarchical depth, was to be reviewed. In the instances where the link was to a section of the site, only the relevant section of the site was to be included. For example, the organisation scheme of 'BBC Ancient History: Greece' only dealt with that section of the site and not that of the parent site 'BBC'.

Finally, it was determined through the piloting phase that few websites readily had available their creation date. To overcome this omission, it was decided to utilise the 'Wayback Machine', a digital archive of the World Wide Web that has archived billions of web pages. While not an ideal source of data for when a website is created, it was determined that at the very least, the 'Wayback Machine' highlights when a website was built no later than.

4.4 Data Collection

Data collection for each subject matter was conducted by going through each website within an identified theme and populating a questionnaire. Each website reviewed was assigned its own questionnaire. At the conclusion of the data collection phase, this data was then transposed into an Excel spreadsheet for analysis.

4.5 Data Analysis

Data was interpreted through bivariate descriptive analysis, a method that explores the 'interrelationships between variables and, hence, possible influences of one variable on another' (Cramer & Howitt, 2011). Once data had been transposed into an Excel sheet, cross-tabulation of data commenced with subject matter being tabulated against organisation scheme with results presented in contingency tables. For example, the major subject theme was tabulated against all eight organisation schemes. Analysis continued across all subject themes and organisation schemes, drilling down into the specifics of each variable.

5.0 Findings

Findings have been broken down into three sections. The first provides an overview of the subject matter, age of website and creator. The second section details the frequency which organisation schemes are employed while the final section looks at the hybrid use of organisation schemes. Additional findings that are too detailed for inclusion within the report are to be found within the Appendices.

5.1 Subject Theme Overview

The following section provides context as to the subject matters reviewed in addition to the age of the websites and the creator.

Subject Matter Overview

In total, 199 website across 6 subject matters were reviewed for their use of organisation schemes (refer Table 3). Four major subject matters had between 38 and 43 websites reviewed across 4-6 minor subject themes (refer Table 2 for minor subject themes). Modern History had 32 websites reviewed while Military History only featured 6 websites reviewed within the 1 minor subject theme. In the instance of Military History, *besthistorysites.net* featured this as a standalone category, hence why the low representation.

Major Subject Matter	# of Minor Subject Themes	# of websites reviewed	total # of websites	% of total
Ancient/Biblical History	6	43	199	21.61
Early American	4	38	199	19.10
Modern American	5	40	199	20.10
European History	4	40	199	20.10
Modern History	6	32	199	16.08
Military History	1	6	199	3.02
Total	26	199	199	100.00

Table 3: Websites Reviewed by Major Subject Matter

Website creation

As detailed within Table 4, websites reviewed across all major subject matters were predominantly first captured by the Internet Archives Wayback Machine pre-2007 (68%). While this finding does not exactly indicate when a website was first developed, it does indicate when a website was created no later than and can therefore be taken as an approximate date of when it was built. One explanation for the age of these websites may be that *besthistorysites.net* began

compiling websites in 2002 and have not removed any over time (evidenced by the large number of dead links). Major subject matters were consistently created from 1997-2017 with the exception of Ancient/Biblical history during 2008-2012 where only 1 website was created.

Major Subject Matter	1997-2002	2003-2007	2008-2012	2013-2017	Undetermined	Total
Ancient/Biblical History	26	8	1	8	0	43
Early American	20	5	5	8	0	38
Modern American	14	5	7	14	0	40
European History	20	9	5	4	2	40
Modern History	15	9	3	5	0	32
Military History	2	1	2	1	0	6
Total	97 (49%)	37 (19%)	23 (12%)	40 (20%)	2 (1%)	199 (100%)

Table 4: Website First Capture Date by Major Subject Matter

Breakdown by Creator

Table 5 identifies the creator of history websites by major subject matter. In total, 12 different creators were identified throughout the research. Media organisations (22%), individuals (21%), universities (17%) and non-profit organisations (15%) were the predominant creators of history websites reviewed as detailed in the far-right column. Conversely, college, government, military and archives were found to have created only 1 or 2 websites.

Media organisations and individuals were found to be heavy creators of all types of subject matter. Media organisations were the most frequent creators of Modern American and Modern History while individuals were more likely to create Early American and European history. The one exception to this trend were Military History websites which were more likely to be created by Non-profit organisations (50%), a figure that is somewhat skewed due to the low number of websites within this subject matter. Universities were consistent creators of history websites across all subject themes reviewed (excluding Military History), perhaps reflecting the diverse range of research interests reflected in academia. Individuals tended to create websites containing older subject matter. Of the 42 websites reviewed that were created by an individual, 34 (81%) focused upon either Ancient/Biblical history, Early American or European History. Taken as a whole, the creators of history websites reviewed is largely consistent with no statistical significance found.

Creator	Ancient/Biblical History	Early American	Modern American	European History	Modern History	Military History	Total
Media Organisation	14 (33%)	4 (11%)	9 (23%)	6 (15%)	11 (34%)	0 (0%)	44 (22%)
Individual	14 (33%)	9 (24%)	5 (13%)	11 (28%)	2 (6%)	1 (17%)	42 (21%)
University	6 (14%)	7 (18%)	8 (20%)	7 (18%)	6 (19%)	0 (0%)	34 (17%)
Non-Profit Organisation	4 (9%)	5 (13%)	1 (3%)	9 (23%)	7 (22%)	3 (50%)	29 (15%)
Library	1 (2%)	4 (11%)	8 (20%)	2 (5%)	2 (6%)	0 (0%)	17 (9%)
Museum	4 (9%)	6 (16%)	2 (5%)	1 (3%)	1 (3%)	0 (0%)	14 (7%)
Educational	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (10%)	1 (3%)	2 (6%)	0 (0%)	7 (4%)
Commercial	0 (0%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	1 (17%)	5 (3%)
College	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3%)	1 (3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (1%)
Government	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (1%)
Military	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3%)	1 (17%)	2 (1%)
Archives	0 (0%)	1 (3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (1%)
Total	43 (100%)	38 (100%)	40 (100%)	40 (100%)	32 (100%)	6 (100%)	199 (100%)

Table 5: Creator v Major Subject Matter

5.2 Organisation Scheme Frequency

The following findings detail both the type of organisation schemes employed within history websites and the frequency in use of one scheme over another.

Organisation Scheme v Subject Theme Major

The types of organisation schemes employed within history websites are those which are frequently found within IA literature (refer Table 6). Furthermore, while organisation schemes do change in their use within history websites, findings indicate that no statistical significance exists as to the frequency of a subject matter employing one type of organisation scheme over another subject matter employing that same scheme.

Topical schemes dominated with 191 websites (96%) employing the scheme, evidence that topical schemes work well for most content and is the most frequently found (Spencer, 2010). Chronological schemes were a clear second in frequency of use with 82 websites (41%) employing it, evidence that history lends itself to the scheme (Morville et al., 2015). Format schemes were employed in nearly a quarter of websites reviewed with many websites containing contemporary subject matters employing the scheme. This would make sense as there is an increased amount of born digital content across various formats as the 20th century progressed. Audience-specific schemes (19%) were more predominant than geographical schemes (15%), predominantly due to a number of websites organising information for teachers separate from that for students. Metaphor schemes (7%) were employed for older subject matter with only Ancient/Biblical history and Early American history featuring the scheme. Task organisation schemes (4%) were seldom featured.

Findings indicate that across the major subject themes reviewed, there was no significant difference as to the use of organisation schemes. Alphabetical schemes exemplify this similarity. Of the 40 European history websites reviewed, 25% of them utilised an alphabetical scheme, 4% above the median. Modern history sites on the other hand, featured an alphabetical scheme 16% of the time, 5% below the median.

Modern history websites were found to be 15% below the median when employing a format scheme, a surprise considering the high creation rate of modern history sites by media organisation like PBS and BBC as detailed in Table 5. It would appear that access to a wide variety of material has not been translated to the use of format as a scheme. Geographical schemes tend to be employed more in Modern history (25%) and Military history (33%) than other subject matters, perhaps best reflecting the subject matter that is found within these particular themes.

Organisation Scheme	Ancient/Biblical (N = 43)	Early American (N = 38)	Modern American (N = 40)	European (N = 40)	Modern (N = 32)	Military (N = 6)	Total (N = 199)
Topical	100% (4%)	97% (1%)	95% (-1%)	90% (-6%)	97% (1%)	100% (4%)	96%
Chronological	33% (-8%)	29% (-12%)	53% (12%)	45% (4%)	44% (3%)	67% (26%)	41%
Format	7% (-18%)	32% (7%)	33% (8%)	40% (15%)	10% (-15%)	33% (8%)	25%
Alphabetical	23% (2%)	24% (3%)	18% (-3%)	25% (4%)	16% (-5%)	17% (-4%)	21%
Audience	23% (4%)	32% (13%)	20% (1%)	13% (-6%)	9% (-10%)	0% (-19%)	19%
Geographical	16% (1%)	8% (-7%)	18% (3%)	5% (-10%)	25% (10%)	33% (18%)	15%
Metaphor	21% (14%)	13% (6%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-7%)	7%
Task	5% (1%)	11% (7%)	3% (-1%)	3% (-1%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	4%

Table 6: Organisation Scheme v Major Subject Theme

Organisation Scheme Component v Subject Theme Major

A more detailed examination within each organisation scheme reveals some interesting points. Content attribution within chronological schemes, relating to the time period of the content, is dominant as highlighted in Table 7. Chronological schemes employ content attribution 39% of the time compared to organising information by when it was created (3%) or through site updates (1%). Images (16%) and Text (10%) were the preferred method of format schemes, perhaps the results of how accessible this content is. Interestingly, 5% of sites grouped primary sources together, keeping them separate from secondary sources. Within alphabetical schemes, indexes (11%) and the use of glossaries (10%) were the most common schemes employed.

While differences within each organisation scheme may be found, they do highlight once more the consistent use of organisation schemes across the subject matters reviewed. While there are minor differences, for the most part, websites employed very similar schemes. It is only the use of an image format within European history websites, a scheme that is employed 22% more than the median that offers a significant difference. However, this may be explained as a result of a number of European art history websites featuring within this section. These results may indicate that historical subject matters bare very similar traits and developers are aware of both the content and how best to organise it (Spencer, 2011).

When a number of the schemes are combined, another point of difference emerges. Content attribution is employed in contemporary rather than older subject matters. Modern American, Military and Modern history are all above the median while Ancient/Biblical, Early American and European history are all below, a difference that can be explained by the type of subject matter within each section. Contemporary subjects are more likely to have established dates and times to events while older subjects are more thematic (Egyptian websites describe daily life for example).

Organisation Scheme	Organisation Scheme Component	Ancient/Biblical (N = 43)	Early American (N = 38)	Modern American (N = 40)	European (N = 40)	Modern (N = 32)	Military (N = 6)	Total (N = 199)
Topical	Subject Matter	100% (4%)	97% (1%)	95% (-1%)	90% (-6%)	97% (1%)	100% (4%)	96%
Chronological	Content Attribution	28% (-11%)	29% (-10%)	53% (14%)	38% (-1%)	44% (5%)	67% (28%)	39%
	Created	2% (1%)	3% (0%)	0% (-3%)	8% (5%)	0% (-3%)	0% (-3%)	3%
	What's New	2% (1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	1%
Format	Video	9% (2%)	3% (-4%)	15% (8%)	3% (-4%)	0% (-7%)	17% (10%)	7%
	Images	7%	18%	13%	38%	9%	33%	16%

		(-9%)	(2%)	(-3%)	(22%)	(-7%)	(17%)	
	Audio	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	13% (9%)	3% (-1%)	3% (-1%)	17% (13%)	4%
	Text	7% (-3%)	11% (1%)	10% (0%)	23% (13%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-10%)	10%
	Primary Sources	0% (-5%)	3% (-2%)	10% (5%)	8% (3%)	3% (-2%)	0% (-5%)	5%
Alphabetical	Encyclopaedia	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	3% (2%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	1%
	Dictionary	2% (1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	3% (2%)	0% (-1%)	1%
	Glossary	14% (4%)	5% (-5%)	3% (-7%)	18% (8%)	13% (3%)	0% (-10%)	10%
	Index	7% (-4%)	18% (7%)	15% (4%)	10% (-1%)	0% (-11%)	17% (6%)	11%
Audience	Knowledge Based	2% (-2%)	0% (-4%)	5% (1%)	8% (4%)	3% (-1%)	0% (-4%)	4%
	Info Need	5% (-1%)	18% (12%)	3% (-3%)	3% (-3%)	0% (-6%)	0% (-6%)	6%
	Educator	9% (-1%)	11% (1%)	15% (5%)	5% (-5)	9% (-1%)	0% (-10%)	10%
Geographical	Map – display	2% (-1%)	3% (0%)	5% (2%)	3% (0%)	0% (-3%)	0% (-3%)	3%
	Map – navigational	5% (-1%)	3% (-3%)	13% (7%)	0% (-6%)	9% (3%)	0% (-6%)	6%
	Text	7% (1%)	3% (-3%)	0% (-6%)	3% (-3%)	16% (10%)	33% (27%)	6%
Metaphor	Labelling	9% (5%)	8% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	4%
	Image	12% (8%)	8% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	4%
Task	Activities	5% (1%)	11% (7%)	3% (-1%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-4%)	4%
	Flip Pages	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	0% (-1%)	3% (2%)	0% (-1%)	0 (-1%)	1%

Table 7: Organisation Scheme Component v Major Subject Matter

Organisation Scheme v Creator

The use of organisation schemes by their creator shows little statistical significance as to subject matters employing one type of organisation scheme over another subject matter employing that same scheme (refer Table 8). Across all creators, there is little difference with topical schemes easily the most preferred method of presenting content. Chronological schemes follow with most creators employing this scheme next, the exception being universities who employ format instead.

Media organisations employ an audience scheme 20% more than the median, reflected by a number of sites that are designed for educational purposes and therefore have resources for both teachers and students. Individuals, on the other hand, are less likely to employ an audience scheme (17% below the median), a reflection perhaps that individuals have a project goal of simply wishing to present information (Spencer, 2011).

Taken on the whole, creators would appear to use the same organisation schemes for the same subject matters. Differences to be found within the table from a percentage perspective largely represent less than a handful of websites reviewed.

Creator	Topical	Chronological	Format	Alphabetical	Audience	Geographical	Metaphor	Task
Media Organisation (N = 44)	98% (2%)	52% (11%)	18% (-7%)	14% (-7%)	39% (20%)	32% (17%)	9% (2%)	2% (-2%)
Individual (N = 42)	98% (2%)	36% (-5%)	33% (8%)	19% (-2%)	2% (-17%)	12% (-3%)	5% (-2%)	0% (-4%)
University (N = 34)	91% (-5%)	35% (-6%)	41% (16%)	29% (8%)	15% (-4%)	6% (-9%)	12% (5%)	3% (-1%)
Non-Profit (N = 29)	97% (1%)	45% (4%)	28% (3%)	31% (10%)	14% (-5%)	17% (2%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-4%)
Library (N = 17)	94% (-2%)	29% (-12%)	18% (-7%)	18% (-3%)	18% (-1%)	0% (-15%)	0% (-7%)	12% (8%)
Museum (N = 14)	100% (4%)	43% (2%)	7% (-18%)	36% (15%)	43% (24%)	7% (-8%)	29% (22%)	21% (17%)
Educational (N = 8)	88% (-9%)	38% (-4%)	13% (-12%)	0% (-21%)	13% (-7%)	0% (-15%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-4%)
Commercial (N = 4)	100% (4%)	75% (34%)	75% (50%)	0% (-21%)	0% (-19%)	25% (10%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-4%)
College (N = 2)	100% (4%)	50% (9%)	50% (25%)	0% (-21%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-15%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-4%)

Government (N = 2)	100% (4%)	0% (-41%)	0% (-25%)	50% (29%)	0% (-19%)	50% (35%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-4%)
Military (N = 2)	100% (4%)	50% (9%)	50% (25%)	0% (-21%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-15%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-4%)
Archives (N = 1)	100% (4%)	0% (-41%)	0% (-25%)	0% (-21%)	100% (81%)	0% (-15%)	0% (-7%)	100% (96%)
Total (N = 199)	96%	41%	25%	21%	19%	15%	7%	4%

Table 8: Organisation Scheme v Creator

5.3 Hybrid Schemes

The following findings detail the use of hybrid schemes found throughout history websites reviewed.

Hybrid Schemes

Table 9 highlights that 32% of websites reviewed employ one organisation scheme, meaning that 68% of websites employ a hybrid scheme for presenting historical information. For websites employing hybrid schemes, the most common finding was the use of 2 schemes, followed by 3 schemes all the way through to six schemes which were found within three website. The use of hybrid schemes is accepted within IA literature, as a combination of them may need to suit the audience, type of content and project’s goals (Spencer, 2010). However, caution is given to the use of hybrid schemes as this approach has the ability to break the mental model of the site for the user, creating confusion as a result (Morville et al., 2015; Wurman et al., 2001). The high level use of hybrid schemes for history websites is interesting as confusion from the user may lead to a misunderstanding of what transpired in the past. Further research into the impact of hybrid schemes is required to determine this however.

# of schemes	# of sites	%
1	64	32%
2	61	30%
3	43	22%
4	20	10%
5	8	4%
6	3	2%
Total	199	100%

Table 9: Hybrid Scheme Use

Hybrid Use by Type

The frequency of organisational scheme use as they occur within hybrid schemes is highlighted in Table 10. When only 1 scheme is employed, 89% of the time a topical scheme is employed. Chronological (6%) and alphabetical (5%) are the only other schemes employed singularly. As hybrid schemes emerge through the use of 2 or more schemes, a similar pattern emerges. Topical schemes dominate, followed by chronological, format, alphabetical and geographical. When 3, 4 or 5 schemes are employed, audience is slightly preferred over that of geographical, the only time this pattern is broken. This finding indicates that hybrid organisation schemes are employed within a consistent pattern, regardless of the number of schemes employed. While there is some variation to this pattern when 5 or 6 schemes are used, this is likely due to the small number of websites that were reviewed in these categories. In total, a consistent approach in the use of hybrid schemes is found.

Organisation Scheme	1 Scheme (N = 64)	2 Schemes (N = 61)	3 Schemes (N = 43)	4 Schemes (N = 20)	5 Schemes (N = 8)	6 Schemes (N = 3)
Topical	57 (89%)	60 (98%)	43 (100%)	20 (100%)	8 (100%)	3 (100%)
Chronological	4 (6%)	22 (36%)	27 (63%)	20 (100%)	6 (75%)	3 (100%)
Format	0 (0%)	15 (25%)	20 (47%)	10 (50%)	3 (38%)	1 (33%)
Alphabetical	3 (5%)	8 (13%)	14 (33%)	9 (45%)	5 (63%)	3 (100%)
Geographical	0 (0%)	7 (11%)	9 (21%)	7 (35%)	5 (63%)	1 (33%)
Audience	0 (0%)	7 (11%)	10 (23%)	11 (55%)	7 (88%)	3 (100%)
Metaphor	0 (0%)	2 (3%)	5 (12%)	2 (10%)	3 (38%)	2 (67%)
Task	0 (0%)	1 (1%)	1 (2%)	1 (5%)	3 (38%)	2 (67%)

Table 10: Hybrid Scheme v Organisation Scheme

Hybrid Use by Subject Theme Major

Findings indicate no statistical significance for history websites employing multiple schemes across the various subject matters reviewed (refer Table 11).

European history websites are 12% more likely to employ 2 schemes while Ancient/Biblical and Early American are 10% less likely to use this approach. Military history websites are more likely to employ 3 schemes, a figure that is possibly misrepresented due to the small sample size while Ancient/Biblical history websites are less likely to employ 3 schemes. For websites employing 4 or more schemes, consistency across all major subject themes is to be found.

Figures for all subject themes are somewhat misrepresented due to the preferred method of using 1 scheme by all subject matters. Ancient/Biblical history websites, for example, are 15% above the median when employing 1 scheme, thereby impacting the use of 2 or more schemes. In total, findings indicate no statistical significance to the use of hybrid schemes.

Creator	1 Scheme (N = 64)	2 Schemes (N = 61)	3 Schemes (N = 43)	4 Schemes (N = 20)	5 Schemes (N = 8)	6 Schemes (N = 3)
Ancient/Biblical (N = 43)	47% (15%)	21% (-10%)	9% (-13%)	12% (2%)	5% (1%)	7% (5%)
Early American (N = 38)	32% (0%)	21% (-10%)	26% (4%)	13% (3%)	8% (4%)	0% (-2%)
Modern American (N = 40)	20% (-12%)	38% (7%)	30% (8%)	10% (0%)	3% (-2%)	0% (-2%)
European (N = 40)	25% (-7%)	43% (12%)	23% (1%)	8% (-3%)	3% (-2%)	0% (-2%)
Modern (N = 32)	41% (9%)	31% (0%)	19% (-3%)	6% (-4%)	3% (-1%)	0% (-2%)
Military (N = 6)	17% (-15%)	33% (2%)	33% (11%)	17% (7%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Total (N = 199)	32%	31%	22%	10%	4%	2%

Table 11: Hybrid Scheme Use by Major Subject Matter

Hybrid Use by Creator

The frequency of hybrid schemes employed by each creator of history websites is highlighted in Table 12. Findings indicate that there is little change in how many schemes creators employ within a history site, an indication perhaps that subject matter ultimately determines the use of schemes and not necessarily those who create the site (Spencer, 2010).

Media organisations, universities and non-profit organisations do not stray too far from the median with non-profit organisations being the greatest at 9% above the median when employing 3 schemes. Individuals like to present information through the use of 1 or 2 schemes, rarely employing 3 or more schemes

within a site, an indication perhaps that either the overall goal of the project is to simply present information (Spencer, 2010) or is an indication of an individual’s skill level when presenting information on a website. Determining this would require further research into this area. The most significant finding relates to libraries who are 21% above the median when employing 1 scheme, possibly due to information being presented topically is the preferred approach and a chronological, format or alphabetical scheme, while functioning ideally as a secondary scheme (Morville et al., 2015), is not necessary.

Creator	1 Scheme (N = 64)	2 Schemes (N = 61)	3 Schemes (N = 43)	4 Schemes (N = 20)	5 Schemes (N = 8)	6 Schemes (N = 3)
Media Organisation (N = 44)	25% (-7%)	27% (-4%)	23% (1%)	14% (4%)	11% (7%)	0% (-2%)
Individual (N = 42)	31% (-1%)	52% (21%)	10% (-12%)	5% (-5%)	0% (-4%)	2% (0%)
University (N = 34)	32% (0%)	26% (-5%)	24% (2%)	12% (2%)	6% (2%)	0% (-2%)
Non-Profit Organisation (N = 29)	28% (-4%)	28% (-3%)	31% (9%)	14% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Library (N = 17)	53% (21%)	24% (-7%)	12% (-10%)	6% (-4%)	6% (2%)	0% (-2%)
Museum (N = 14)	21% (-11%)	29% (-2%)	21% (-1%)	14% (4%)	0% (-4%)	14% (12%)
Educational (N = 8)	63% (31%)	25% (-6%)	13% (-10%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Commercial (N = 4)	25% (-7%)	0% (-31%)	50% (28%)	25% (15%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
College (N = 2)	50% (18%)	0% (-31%)	50% (28%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Government (N = 2)	50% (18%)	0% (-31%)	50% (28%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Military (N = 2)	50% (18%)	0% (-31%)	50% (28%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Archives (N = 1)	0% (-32%)	0% (-31%)	100% (78%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Total	32%	31%	22%	10%	4%	2%

Table 12: Hybrid Scheme v Creator

6.0 Discussion

Research findings indicate that while historical subject matters do employ different organisational schemes, there is no evidence that one particular subject matter favours one scheme over another. The following discussion reviews the objectives of the research project and the research question itself against the findings from the data collection and analysis phase.

Types of organisation schemes employed

Research indicates that the types of organisation schemes employed within existing history websites are established within IA literature and practices and does not change dependent upon the historical subject matter involved. There were few surprises as topical, chronological, format, alphabetical, audience-specific, geographical, task and metaphor schemes were all employed (refer Table 6). Findings indicate that neither the creator of the website nor the creation date bears any relevance as to when a scheme is used, as they were found to be employed across all creators and age periods with a large degree of similarity.

Findings do indicate the possibility for another organisation scheme to be created, employed specifically within history websites. Primary sources are the basis for historical understanding, evidence of the past that may exist in the form of a diary, manuscript or recording. A secondary source is the narrative developed from a collection of primary sources, be it a book or journal article. Together, primary and secondary sources create historical narratives and understanding. Of all history websites reviewed, 5% organised information into a primary source category (refer Table 7). In many cases, primary sources were found to be spread within another scheme – topical, chronological or format, missing out on being categorised together. In some instances, the reviewer found it was very unclear as to what constituted a primary source from a secondary one. Spencer (2009) acknowledges that organising information is ‘ultimately an imperfect and messy undertaking’ as interpretations of which information should be displayed within which scheme is considered. Considering the important role primary sources play in understanding the past, it is a little surprising that more emphasis was not given to employing primary sources as an organisation scheme across all history websites reviewed. Further research into this area is a possibility.

Frequency of organisation scheme

Findings indicate that the frequency of use of an organisation scheme is not dependent upon either the subject matter involved, the creator of the website or when the website was built. While there are differences within the findings, these may be classified as minor and are not statistically significant. Similarly, data analysis for each minor subject theme highlights no significant findings (refer Appendix 11.2). The following discussion details the use of the most prominent organisation schemes found within history websites from the most frequently employed to the least.

Topical Scheme

Topical schemes are the most heavily used with 96% of websites reviewed employing this scheme. In instances where only 1 scheme was employed (refer Table 10), 89% of websites employed a topical scheme. Morville et al (2015) argue that topical schemes are ‘one of the most useful and challenging approaches’ when organising information and is a classification that works well for almost any content (Spencer, 2010). History is a subject matter that is ideal for topical breakdown. University courses for history are constructed around particular historical subject matter while bookshops organise their

books similarly. The very nature of the subject matter leads to research and presenting to be conducted within constructs that aid contextualisation and understanding. It is little wonder that these principles have carried over into the digital realm of websites.

Chronological Scheme

Chronological schemes is the most prevalent scheme used after that of topical with 41% of history websites employing this scheme (refer Table 6). In most instances, a chronological scheme was used to attribute events as to when they happened (refer Table 7). The scheme is easy to use, design and implement (Spencer, 2010) with certain types of information, history being one, that lends itself to the scheme (Morville et al., 2015). Understanding the past often requires contextualising what happened within a narrative. Chronological schemes provide a 'framework from which changes can be observed and comparisons made' (Wurman et al., 2001). To understand how close the world came to nuclear war during the Cuban Missile Crisis requires knowledge of the events that led up. History requires context and it is little wonder that chronological schemes are so readily employed.

Format Scheme

Format is the third most used organisation schemes within history websites reviewed as 25% organised information this way (refer Table 6). Spencer (2010) argues that format schemes are a great way to show the different types of information available within a website as long as this is how the audience wants to view it. A format scheme makes sense to employ within history websites, especially those that have a subject matter set in the 20th Century. Video, audio and images are readily available to historians and the ease of adding these formats to a website makes their use more common and helps contextualise the past. As an example, military history can often tell the narrative of a battle through the use of maps. By allowing the user to access maps within a format scheme, an understanding may be gained of the historical situation.

Alphabetical Scheme

Organising information via an alphabetical scheme was employed in 21% of history websites reviewed (refer Table 6). An objective scheme that can be used for almost any type of information if people know what they are looking for (Spencer, 2010), it is a little surprising that so few websites used this approach. One explanation may be due to the high use of topical schemes to present content, potentially nullifying the need to include an alphabetical scheme at the same time which would require more work on the behalf of the creator. For users who have trouble understanding content via another scheme however, an alphabetical approach can assist greatly (Wurman et al., 2001). Secondly, Google and the incorporation of search within sites may also be a factor. Alphabetical schemes are great if people know what they are looking for (Morville et al., 2015), relying upon this approach rather than designing a purpose built glossary or index, saving time and money.

Audience-Specific Scheme

Audience-specific schemes were found within 19% of history websites reviewed (refer Table 6). While fraught with the perils of personalising information (Morville et al., 2015), audience-specific schemes do work if there are clearly defined boundaries between audiences who are aware as to which group they belong to (Spencer, 2010). The use of an audience-scheme was largely determined by websites having content for students in one section and lesson plans for educators in another. While history websites are able to be broken down by audience, assumptions are made when doing so as to which

piece of information belongs where. While there is value in customising content to specific user groups (Morville et al., 2015), as in the case of educational history websites, more research is perhaps required to determine the impact that this scheme has upon a users' understanding of the past.

Geographical Scheme

Geographical schemes are objective in nature and are fairly easy to use as long as the location of an event can be agreed upon (Morville et al., 2015) with 15% of history websites reviewed employing this method. Spencer (2010) argues that for geographical schemes to work effectively, the audience must want it and they must also understand how to use it. The low use of geographical schemes is somewhat surprising as a location of an event plays a key role in understanding what took place with military history websites being a prime example. The Western Front in the First World War was an entirely different theatre to that of the Eastern Front. Kalbach (2007) argues that some content lends itself to being organised geographically and history is a prime example of this.

Hybrid Schemes

Findings determine that the employment of hybrid schemes within a history site is not dependent upon the subject matter involved or the creator of the website. Nor does the year that the website was first captured by the 'Wayback Machine' correlate to hybrid scheme use (refer Appendix 11.3).

, the creator or the year the website was developed. While small differences do exist within the results, similar to the frequency of schemes being used, these may be classified as minor and bear no statistical significance. Likewise, there was little difference between subject matters when it can to either the use of hybrid schemes or which schemes were more likely to be used.

Digital environments are wonderfully flexible, offering the opportunity to organise information through multiple organisation schemes (Morville et al., 2015). Findings support this statement with 67% of websites employing 2 or more schemes in a hybrid environment. Spencer (2010) argument that there are no hard and fast rules when it comes to classification and a hybrid scheme is appropriate is negated by the understanding that 'people like information to be organised consistently' (Garrett, 2001). Historical subject matter is often complex, detailed and interwoven. A website focusing upon the Cold War will have content covering multiple decades across numerous geographical boundaries along political and social lines. While a hybrid scheme makes sense to use in this situation, there is a chance that a deeply layered hybrid site will result, breaking the mental model of the site for the user (Morville et al., 2015). The prevalent use of hybrid schemes within history websites reviewed requires further research to determine the impact that such schemes have upon the user.

Findings indicate that when 1 organisation scheme is employed, a topical approach is the preferred method (89%). This finding runs counter to Morville et al (2015) suggestion that 'few information environments are organised solely by topic'. One explanation may be that the depth of the history websites reviewed was not significant and a simple topical scheme was sufficient. Another possibility relates to the website creator being unaware of how to organise information within a website and simply chose the most common scheme. Further research into this finding would be required.

As a second, third and fourth scheme is introduced, results highlighting a similar pattern emerges. When a second scheme is introduced to that of topical, the preferred scheme is that of chronological (refer Table 10). When a third scheme is introduced, it is format. These rankings are similar to that found when comparing organisation schemes to subject themes (refer Table 6). While figures are

somewhat skewed due to the high use of hybrid schemes, it does indicate that organisation schemes are consistently employed within hybrid schemes across various subject matters.

It is interesting to note that following topical schemes, the order of preference for a second, third, fourth and largely fifth scheme are represented by exact organisation schemes. Exact schemes are easy to design and implement, 'there's nothing to argue about. It just is' (Covert, 2014). Their ranking in terms of use within a hybrid scheme is supported by the literature that states they offer great value as secondary schemes (Morville et al., 2015; Spencer, 2010). Findings would therefore highlight that the frequent use of hybrid schemes within history websites aligns directly to what the literature says about these schemes. While their use may be prevalent, their impact upon the mental model of the site for the user is unknown and requires further research into this area.

7.0 Limitations

Limitations within this research project predominantly lie within either the classification/age of websites as found within *besthistorysites.net* or through the lack of statistical software (SPSS for instance) for data analysis.

Website classification within *besthistorysites.net* determined which subject matter each website was assigned, an outcome that was not always clear nor precise. Cold War related websites, for example, appeared in both the category of Modern American and that of Modern history. A close examination of the types of websites found within each category provided no insight as to how this classification system worked. Similarly, the decision to split the American history category into Early American and Modern American essentially created two categories that contained modern subject matter in different categories. Spencer's (2009) claim that classification is an imperfect undertaking is clearly exhibited in how *besthistorysites.net* organise their lists. A different person organising the list may have provided different findings or insights into the use of organisation schemes.

A significant proportion of the websites reviewed are quite old, built in the early days of the web when best-practice approaches were still being researched and developed. Awareness of the types of organisation schemes available and how best to employ them was still growing, the result of which was many sites were simple copies of others in how to arrange information. Findings would appear to be skewed as a result.

A lack of access to statistical software (SPSS for instance) required data analysis to be conducted within Microsoft Excel. The vast amount of raw data made cross-tabulation and third-party analysis quite complex and when coupled with the researcher's first attempt at quantitative data analysis, findings and insights may have been missed as a result.

8.0 Recommendations

A number of further research opportunities have been born relating to the use of both primary sources as a scheme as well as that of audience along with conducting the study on more recently developed websites.

Primary sources are critical to understanding the past and form the basis through which historical knowledge is acquired. Findings indicate that across all history websites reviewed, very few (5%) organised primary sources within a standalone category. Instead, primary sources were often spread throughout another scheme – topical, chronological or format. Further research could examine the

use and role of primary sources within history websites in the form of qualitative studies that explore the use and impact of primary sources to the understanding and development of historical knowledge.

History websites were found to employ audience-specific themes 25% of the time across all subject matters, often dividing information between student and educator needs. Throughout the data collection phase, the researcher determined that in many instances the boundaries between audiences appeared confusing, supporting the arguments found within the literature on the dangers of organising content according to audience (Morville et al., 2015; Spencer, 2010). Further research into how history websites may best employ an audience-specific scheme could develop a greater understanding towards not only the use of the scheme but also how this scheme may impact an understanding of the past.

Conducting research on contemporary history websites could yield a different insight into the use of organisation schemes. Further study on history websites that have been developed within the past 5 years may provide different findings and indicate how far historians have come in organising content for the web. For example, websites built by the *Roy Rosenzweig Center for History and New Media* are purposively built by trained digital historians that are contemporary and host a wide range of subject matters.

9.0 Conclusion

This research project reviewed the organisation schemes of history websites across a wide range of subject matters from *besthistorysites.net*. While digital historians have focused upon emergent technological tools when presenting the past, how information may be organised within a website has been neglected. Meanwhile, information architects have focused their organisation skills and energies upon projects that have overlooked the role of organisation schemes within history websites. The current research project fills this gap.

The research question asked: Do organisational scheme(s) employed within history websites change dependent upon the subject matter involved? The answer is no. While organisation schemes are employed at varying frequencies, they are not at all related to the subject matter. Likewise, there was no difference to be found between the creator of the website, nor when the website was built. Instead, a consistent pattern emerges across all fields of history subjects that were reviewed.

Findings indicate that while organisation schemes found within the review are based within existing literature, the prospect of a primary source organisation scheme to be employed for history websites emerges. Further research into this possibility is required however.

The frequency of employing various organisation scheme largely follows what has been discussed within the existing literature. Topical schemes are dominant throughout all subject matters reviewed while chronological, format, alphabetical and geographical schemes are more likely to act as a secondary scheme.

Finally, research determined a high level of hybrid scheme use through all subject matters reviewed in a consistent pattern. Creators of websites were as likely to use a hybrid scheme for Early American history as they were for Modern history.

While the research question and objectives of the project have been emphatically answered, further research is required into the use of organisation schemes and their impact upon a users' understanding of the past.

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11.0 Appendix

11.1 Questionnaire

Website Information

Website Name	
Website URL	
Creator (select one):	
• Museum	
• University	
• Library	
• Centre	
• Media organisation	
• Non-profit organisation	
• Individual	
• Other (specify)	
Major Subject Grouping	
Secondary Subject Grouping	
Location of host (by country)	
Which year was the website created?	
Which year was the website last updated?	
Content featured within the website:	
Yes/No	
• Text	
• Images	
• Videos	
• Audio	
• Maps	
• Other (specify)	

Organisation Schemes

Which of the following organisational schemes are employed within the website? **Yes/No unless otherwise stated**

Organisation Scheme	Home Page	Child Page(s)
Alphabetical scheme		
• Encyclopaedia		
• Dictionary		
• Glossary		
• Index		
• Other (specify)		
Chronological scheme		
• Content attribution		

• Other (specify)		
Geographical scheme		
• Map (displays information only).		
• Map (navigational)		
• Text-based		
• Other (specify)		
Topical scheme		
• Subject matter		
• Other (specify)		
Task-oriented scheme		
• Activities		
• Other (specify)		
Audience-specific scheme		
• Subject knowledge based		
• User information need		
• Other (specify)		
Metaphor-driven scheme		
• Labelling imagery		
• Interactive image		
• Other (specify)		
Format scheme		
• Video		
• Picture		
• Audio		
• Articles		
• Other (specify)		
Other scheme (specify)		

11.2 Organisation Scheme v Minor Subject Theme

		Alphabetical	Chronological	Geographical	Topical	Task-Oriented	Audience-Specific	Metaphor	Format
Ancient /Biblical	Egypt (N = 12)	25% (4%)	42% (1%)	8% (-7%)	100% (4%)	8% (4%)	25% (6%)	33% (26%)	25% (-3%)
	Greece (N = 13)	23% (2%)	38% (-3%)	31% (16%)	100% (4%)	8% (4%)	23% (4%)	15% (8%)	23% (-5%)
	Rome (N = 9)	22% (1%)	22% (-19%)	11% (-4%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	22% (3%)	22% (15%)	33% (5%)
	China (N = 3)	0% (-21%)	0% (-41%)	0% (-15%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-28%)
	India (N = 3)	0% (-21%)	33% (-8%)	33% (18%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	33% (14%)	33% (26%)	0% (-28%)
	Judaism (N = 3)	33% (12%)	33% (-8%)	33% (18%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	33% (14%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-28%)
	Total (N = 43)	21% (0%)	33% (-8%)	19% (4%)	100% (4%)	5% (1%)	23% (4%)	21% (14%)	21% (-7%)
Early American	Pre-Colonial (N = 9)	33% (9%)	11% (-30%)	0% (-15%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	11% (-8%)	11% (4%)	44% (16%)
	Colonial (N = 15)	40% (16%)	33% (-8%)	7% (-8%)	93% (-3%)	7% (3%)	33% (14%)	20% (13%)	27% (-1%)
	Early Republic (N = 8)	0% (-24%)	38% (-4%)	13% (-3%)	100% (4%)	13% (9%)	38% (19%)	0% (-7%)	25% (-3%)
	US Constitution (N = 6)	0% (-24%)	33% (-8%)	17% (2%)	100% (4%)	33% (29%)	50% (31%)	17% (10%)	33% (5%)
	Total (N = 38)	24% (3%)	29% (-12%)	8% (-7%)	97% (1%)	11% (7%)	32% (13%)	13% (6%)	32% (4%)
Modern American	Progressive Era (N = 6)	33% (15%)	50% (9%)	17% (2%)	83% (-13%)	0% (-4%)	33% (14%)	0% (-7%)	33% (5%)
	Roaring 20s (N = 7)	29% (11%)	43% (2%)	14% (-1%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	14% (-5%)	0% (-7%)	29% (1%)
	Great Depression (N = 5)	20% (2%)	60% (19%)	20% (5%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	20% (1%)	0% (-7%)	60% (32%)
	Civil Rights Movement	8% (-10%)	42% (1%)	17% (2%)	83% (-13%)	8% (4%)	25% (6%)	0% (-7%)	33% (5%)

	(N = 12)								
	Cold War Era (N = 10)	10% (-8%)	70% (29%)	20% (5%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	10% (-9%)	0% (-7%)	20% (-8%)
	Total (N = 40)	18% (-3%)	53% (12%)	18% (3%)	93% (-3%)	3% (-2%)	20% (1%)	0% (-7%)	33% (5%)
European	Medieval (N = 12)	42% (17%)	33% (-8%)	8% (-7%)	75% (-21%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	42% (14%)
	Renaissance (N = 12)	(17%) (-8%)	42% (1%)	8% (-7%)	92% (-4%)	8% (4%)	25% (6%)	0% (-7%)	33% (5%)
	Scientific (N = 6)	33% (8%)	67% (26%)	0% (-15%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	67% (39%)
	Reformation (N = 10)	10% (-15%)	50% (9%)	0% (-15%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	20% (1%)	0% (-7%)	30% (2%)
	Total (N = 40)	25% (4%)	45% (4%)	5% (-10%)	90% (-6%)	3% (-2%)	13% (-7%)	0% (-7%)	40% (12%)
Modern	World War I (N = 3)	33% (17%)	100% (59%)	33% (18%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-28%)
	World War II (N = 9)	0% (-16%)	22% (-19%)	22% (7%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-28%)
	Hitler (N = 5)	0% (-16%)	20% (-21%)	0% (-15%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	20% (-8%)
	Stalin (N = 4)	0% (-16%)	50% (9%)	0% (-15%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	25% (6%)	0% (-7%)	25% (-3%)
	Middle East Conflict (N = 5)	20% (4%)	60% (19%)	60% (45%)	80% (-16%)	0% (-4%)	20% (1%)	0% (-7%)	20% (-8%)
	Cold War Era (N = 6)	50% (34%)	33% (-8%)	33% (18%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	17% (-2%)	0% (-7%)	0% (-28%)
	Total (N = 32)	16% (-5%)	41% (0%)	25% (10%)	97% (3%)	0% (-4%)	9% (-10%)	0% (-7%)	9% (-19%)
Military History	Military History (N = 6)	17% (0%)	67% (26%)	33% (18%)	100% (4%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-7%)	33% (5%)
Total	(N = 199)	21%	41%	15%	95%	4%	19%	7%	28%

Table 13: Organisation Scheme v Minor Subject Theme

11.3 Hybrid Scheme Use v Creation Date

	1 Scheme	2 Schemes	3 Schemes	4 Schemes	5 Schemes	6 schemes
1997-2002	32% (0%)	31% (0%)	19% (0%)	11% (1%)	5% (1%)	2% (0%)
2003-2007	30% (-2%)	32% (1%)	24% (5%)	5% (-5%)	5% (1%)	3% (1%)
2008-2012	39% (7%)	26% (-5%)	26% (7%)	9% (-1%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
2013-2017	30% (-2%)	30% (-1%)	25% (6%)	13% (3%)	3% (-2%)	0% (-2%)
Undetermined	50% (18%)	50% (19%)	0% (-19%)	0% (-10%)	0% (-4%)	0% (-2%)
Total	32%	31%	22%	10%	4%	2%

Table 14: Hybrid Scheme Use v Creation Date

12.0 Reflection

Reflecting upon this project, I feel that there are two distinct learning outcomes. The first relates to the types of organisation schemes employed within history websites. I was a little surprised by the consistency found but in hindsight believe this shows the strength of organisation principles in the field of Information Architecture. Secondly, this was my first quantitative research project and an understanding of the process involved has been gained. I have recorded what I felt to be my strengths and weaknesses throughout and will be able to apply moving forward.

There are a number of strengths to this report which I hope are identifiable throughout. I have a passion for both history and information architecture and information organisation and I hope this shows in the scope and depth of the literature. A lot was learnt from my first research project last year and I feel that I have strengthened the research approach considerable as a result. Finally, I feel that I set myself up for success from the very start by keeping the research project manageable. Again this is something which I learnt from last year and it enabled me to engage with the literature and present a stronger project overall as a result.

Weaknesses mainly relate to experience. I feel that the data analysis was lacking as I didn't have access to SPSS and needed to rely upon Excel to determine findings. The large volume of data at times became overwhelming and I do feel that I missed an opportunity to gain some valuable insights. Having said this, I believe that if I were to conduct the same analysis from scratch it would be considerably improved. It is a learning curve. Secondly, upon reflection I don't feel that my critical reasoning is as strong as I would like it to be. I believe that this comes back to how I synthesis the findings and relate these back to the findings. Again, it's a learning curve and I will be better for it next time.

Moving forward there are a few skill areas that I would like to improve upon. The first concerns data analysis. There is little point in conducting quantitative research if it isn't effectively analysed. Further reading into data analysis and practice will help overcome this however. Secondly, I feel that I am in a better position to take a holistic view of the entire research process, strengthening each step and improving the research and findings as a whole. This is a skill that can only be developed by gaining experience.

Reflecting upon the entire project and the report in particular, I feel that I have meet a large amount of the assessment criteria to a high degree. My understanding of the topic and use of literature is high, I have provided a comprehensive research approach and the discussion and conclusion do indeed answer the research question and meet the objectives of the project. One notable exception as mentioned however is critical reasoning which I feel drags down my mark overall.

Grade 7 – 87%